

Southern California CSU DNP Consortium

California State University, Fullerton
California State University, Long Beach
California State University, Los Angeles

INCREASING COMMUNICATION SKILLS OF COMMUNITY CARE HOSPICE
NURSES USING ELNEC COMMUNICATION MATERIALS

A DOCTORAL PROJECT

Submitted in Partial Fulfillment of the Requirements

For the degree of

DOCTOR OF NURSING PRACTICE

By

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ABSTRACT

Introduction: Palliative and hospice care nurses provide specialized healthcare services for patients at the end of life (EOL) and support their families during this time. Positive communication skills are paramount in the delivery of quality care at EOL. Studies have shown that nurses' knowledge of best communication strategies and their self-efficacy in effectively communicating with patients and families improved after participating in End-of-Life Nursing Education Consortium (ELNEC) and COMFORT communication training. **Aim:** The aim of this project was to evaluate a training program based on ELNEC and COMFORT communication to improve communication skills of nurses working in a community hospice care setting. **Methods:** Nine nurses employed at a community care hospice center in Southern California participated in an ELNEC focused educational training program involving two, two-hour sessions. A pre- and posttest design was used. Knowledge of EOL communication strategies and self-efficacy in communications skills were assessed, and a program evaluation was conducted. **Results:** Two-tailed, paired sample T-test analyses were conducted. Pre and posttest results related to the communication training showed significant increases in knowledge of EOL ($P < .001$) and participant's self-efficacy ($P = .009$). Participants' evaluation of the program indicated a high level of satisfaction and perceived improved confidence in their communicating skills. They also reported practicing communication skills through role play was beneficial. **Conclusion:** Training using the ELNEC communication Module 6 and COMFORT communication curriculum was an effective teaching strategy that improved nurses' knowledge, skill, and confidence about communicating with patients and their families during hospice/palliative and EOL care. The use of ELNEC training modules is recommended as the standard for educational preparation of hospice care nurses.

Keywords: hospice and palliative care nursing, end-of-life care, hospice nurses, End-of-Life Nursing Education Consortium (ELNEC) and COMFORT Communication

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Background

Palliative care provides a specialized healthcare service that has become a vital component in promoting quality medical and nursing care to patients with serious illnesses (Ferrell et al., 2018; 2007) and support for their families (Dahlin & Wittenberg, 2019; Ferrell et al., 2018). In 2017, 20.4 million people worldwide were diagnosed with a life-limiting illness (Buller et al., 2019). When patients have advanced or progressive illnesses, palliative care helps families focus on maximizing Quality of Life (QOL) and optimizing the functional well-being (Lynch et al., 2012) of their loved one (National Comprehensive Cancer Network [NCCN], 2015). Palliative care services assist in the management of pain and other symptoms associated (Nguyen et al., 2014) with the patient's disease process. This care also focuses on a patient's emotional and mental health as well as spiritual and social needs. Palliative care is an umbrella term used to describe care provided to patients who are chronically and or terminally ill and includes End-of-life (EOL) care. Palliative care is a patient and family-centered care approach that enhances QOL by respecting the patient's values and goals (Lynch et al., 2012) during the EOL experience. Hospice and palliative care programs, as well as the healthcare providers delivering health services, have the responsibility to ensure that the care they provide is consistent with national standards of high-quality care (Connor, 2013).

Patients who are dying are often given palliative care plans, which are determined through a holistic assessment of the patient's needs. A palliative care plan is based on patients' and families' goals for care and values associated with the dying process. The care plan involves helping patients and their families gain a better understanding of the disease process using evidence-based approaches to control the patients' symptoms, ensures best practices in

communication among the care team, patient, and family (Goldsmith et al., 2020), and provides coordinated, holistic patient care (Lynch et al., 2012).

Palliative care involves a continuum of healthcare services, which provide a wide array of interventions that can be delivered in any setting with an emphasis on pain and other symptom management, communication, and coordinated care. (Hartjes, 2015; Agency for Healthcare Research and Quality [AHRQ], 2011; www.scribd.com, 2012). Hospice care and EOL care are subsets of palliative care. EOL care involves symptom control management or comfort care for patients who are at the last stage of their terminal disease. At the same time, hospice is a care delivery system for patients in the last months of life who have chosen QOL as a primary goal of care (www.scribd.com, 2012). This care is provided primarily in specific settings, including homes, specialized inpatient units, and skilled nursing facilities (AHRQ, 2011; Grant et al., 2013; Hartjes, 2015).

Hospice care is provided when a patient typically has six months or less to live. Hospice is high quality, compassionate care that helps patients live as full a life (Spicer et al., 2015) as possible with dignity when a cure is not available (National Hospice and Palliative Care Organization [NHPCO], n.d.a.; 2018; National Cancer Institute, 2012). Hospice care philosophy is based on the understanding that death is part of the life cycle (Dadfar et al., 2015) and that careful management of physical, psychosocial, and spiritual symptoms will promote the best possible QOL for patients and family system (Cohen & Nirenberg, 2011). More than 80% of Americans would prefer to die at home (Lee et al., 2017), but only 25% of deaths occur at home (Buller et al., 2019).

Caregivers perform a vital role in the care of their loved ones who are dying. Research suggests that EOL care is intensive, which makes decision-making stressful (Ornstein et al.,

2017). The intensive nature of EOL care is due in part to the stress experienced by caregivers who watch their family members suffer pain, emotional stress, fear, anxiety, and other physical and mental symptoms. Caregivers experience high levels of depression and anxiety in caring for their loved ones while in hospice (Ornstein et al., 2017). Thus, caregivers and their healthcare providers need to communicate effectively in order to relieve the stress and anxiety that is often experienced with caregivers, who are always aware of the fact that their loved one will be dying imminently. A critical clinical element of quality hospice/palliative care is effective communication. Therefore, nurses must be prepared to communicate intentionally and provide quality primary palliative nursing care across all clinical settings (Bishop et al., 2019).

Problem Statement

Community Care Hospice (CCH) is a palliative care Medicare-certified and Joint Commission accredited facility serving the community of Southern California since 2003. The CCH falls under the purview of the Centers for Medicare and Medicaid Services (CMS). The CCH provides specialized care for people who were terminally ill, which involves a team-oriented approach that addresses the medical, physical, social, emotional, and spiritual needs of the patients and their families and caregivers. The administrators and staff of CCH are committed to providing comfort care marked by dignity and respect for their patients who are at the EOL. CCH's mission is to serve the community and provide quality care to their patients and family support. Nursing care at CCH is available seven days a week, 24 hours per day, and is provided on an intermittent basis with visits scheduled dependent on the patient's advance care plan (ACP). CCH has a multidisciplinary team that includes a medical director, executive director, six hospice nurses, a case manager, a social worker, four hospice aides, a spiritual counselor, a dietician, a part-time pharmacist, and five volunteers. CCH also provides medical

equipment, supplies, and medications to facilitate patients' comfort. Patients with complex medical or mental health needs are provided nursing care that is outlined through policy and organizational procedures.

During discussions with the Executive Director of CCH, the project author learned that the CCH care providers face daily challenges when interacting with patients and families, which typically revolve around caregiver and family member communication and symptom management. These challenges usually involve how to best communicate with families regarding EOL care and the dying processes and help caregivers understand their roles in pain control and other symptom management. Family caregivers must understand these processes in order to assist with the physical, mental, and spiritual care (Wynne, 2013) needed for their loved one who is cared for in the home setting.

Hospice nurses are in a position to help educate caregivers about their role and must demonstrate respect, honesty, flexibility, and empathy in their interactions with family members (Ornstein et al., 2017). Caregivers are often anxious about administering potent pharmacological agents to their loved ones for pain control. A key issue that hospice nurses face is how best to educate and direct family caregivers about their critical role in administering medications to ensure effective pain management at EOL. At the same time, nurses must be skilled in communication strategies to alleviate caregivers' fear of overmedicating or harming their loved ones. Nurses also need to educate patients and their families to help them understand the pharmacological therapies a patient receives to control pain and other symptoms.

A hospice nurse educates caregivers about the active role they assume in caring for their loved one at EOL and do so in a manner that empowers and supports a caregiver who is taking on a new role and collaborating with the hospice nurse to provide care. Caregivers are frequently

called upon to become competent in assessing the need for pain control and other symptoms related to the dying process. They may also be expected to develop, rather quickly, skills associated with caregiving, such as administering medications or performing procedures (e.g. suctioning or stoma care). The patient, caregiver, and hospice nurse partnership role during EOL care requires the nurse to apply skillful, intentional, and compassionate communication techniques (Chi et al., 2016). The End-of-Life Nursing Education Consortium (ELNEC) communication model is an evidence-based resource that can be used to train and improve hospice nurses' competence around communication at EOL.

ELNEC is a nationally, and internationally, recognized educational initiative that provides modules for training clinicians, including nurses, in caring for patients at the EOL (Dahlin & Wittenberg, 2019). This project author is a trained ELNEC trainer, believed that adopting the communication principles of ELNEC, namely Module 6, which focuses on enhancing communication skills at ENL would enhance the knowledge and skills of the providers who work with patients at CCH. In addition, the project author sought to integrate COMFORT^{TMSM} communication principles with the ELNEC communication training to enhance the training offered to nurses at the CCH center.

Purpose Statement

The purpose of this quality improvement (Q.I.) project was to initiate, implement, and evaluate an educational program focused on communication training that integrates ELNEC and the COMFORT^{TMSM} curricula for hospice nurses at a community care hospice center that provides care and support to patients and their caregivers at EOL.

Project Objectives

1. Adapt the ELNEC and COMFORT educational materials for CCH hospice nurses with a focus on best practices in communication with patients and families at EOL and an emphasis on patients' goals and values.
2. Implement elements of the ELNEC and COMFORT communication modules with a focus on communication relevant to pharmacological and nonpharmacological interventions that alleviate physical and psychological symptoms associated with EOL.
3. Initiate and evaluate the effect of the training on the hospice nurse's knowledge of communication with patients and their families at EOL.

Theoretical Framework

The framework selected to guide this DNP project was the Plan, Do, Study, Act (PDSA) model. The PDSA model was initially developed by Edward Deming in 1990 (Connor, 2013) and provides a structured approach for implementing changes when conducting a quality improvement project. The PDSA Model is widely used as it allows for change to occur in cycles while being able to improve the intervention at each cycle; it is currently the tool recommended by the Institute for Healthcare Improvement (IHI) to train those trying to implement change (<http://www.ihl.org/resources/Pages/Tools/PlanDoStudyActWorksheet.aspx>)

The PDSA Model involves four iterative but sequential stages. The first stage is the Plan stage, where the project author identifies issues and develops a plan for change. The second stage is the Do stage, during which stakeholders carry out the change and measure its impact. The third stage is the Study stage. In this stage, before and after data are compared to determine the effect of the change. The fourth stage is the Act stage, in which stakeholders plan the next cycle or further implementation based on the findings obtained during the Study stage (Connor, 2013).

The PDSA model proposes that changes occur in smaller focused cycles, and therefore Deming (2016) suggested that the PDSA cycle be performed repeatedly so that the intervention is fine-tuned at each cycle. The PDSA model is flexible and adaptable for use in various healthcare settings (Reed & Card 2016).

Randhawa et al. (2011) used the PDSA methodology for performance improvement in their study which aimed at implementing and sustaining an evidence-based practice improvement to reduce pediatric cardiopulmonary arrests (Randhawa et al., 2011). They demonstrated that problem areas related to ineffective communication were reduced at the organizational level as well at the nurse level by improving nurses' ability to communicate more effectively to address patient care needs. Similarly, the PDSA process was used in this DNP study to improve the quality-of-care EOL patients received. Thus, the PDSA framework provided the structure and guided the process of enhancing the EOL related communication skillsets of nurses participating in this project.

Integration of the PDSA Model to Improve Communication

In the present project, the author utilized the PDSA Model to implement and evaluate the effect of using the ELNEC/COMFORT Communication-based modules on hospice nurses in providing care to EOL patients. The PDSA model involves a series of "rapid change cycles," which require considerable preparation to properly execute the model's steps successfully (Baxley et al., 2011). The PDSA Model application in this project is depicted in Appendix A.

The first stage of this project was to plan. The Plan stage involved project preparation, which included the obtaining buy in from CCH Stakeholders to secure the needed support, facilitation, and implementation of change. The plan to implement and the assessment tools for the communication training were done in consultation with the stakeholders.

The second stage of this project, Do, involved training and teaching the materials in the ELNEC Module 6 Communication and the COMFORT ^{TMSM} curriculum to the CCH nurses. The ELNEC program provided these nurses with information about the best practice strategies to use to increase communication skills that are critical when assessing patients' QOL issues and concerns during discussions with patient and or family members. Positive communication skills allow nurses to effectively educate patients and their caregivers about pharmacological and nonpharmacological interventions that alleviate physical and psychological symptoms associated with EOL.

All the hospice nurses in the CCH participated in the project. Their participation began with the completion of the pre surveys assessing their knowledge and perception of self-efficacy related to communication skills regarding EOL. The pre-survey consisted of questionnaires, using percentage scores to establish baseline knowledge levels about EOL issues, and communication skill surveys that used a 5-point Likert response scale to ascertain perception of self-efficacy in communication skills. In addition, hospice nurses were asked to participate in narrative engagements about case studies related to hospice practice and to describe their feelings about communication and EOL. The hospice nurses also completed a pre-survey to obtain information about the nurses' demographic background. The hospice nurses then participated in the ELNEC Module 6 Communication and COMFORT ^{TMSM} training. Upon conclusion of the training, the hospice nurse completed the post surveys, which consisted of the same narrative questions completed during the pre-survey, along with the post-questionnaires, and the communication skills survey that used a 5-point Likert scale, and questions evaluating the ELNEC communication training.

The third stage, Study, involved reflection. During this stage, pre and post data were compared to determine if the training led to improved knowledge of best communication practices and their application by hospice nurses in EOL communications with patients and families. The CCH hospice nurses were asked to reflect (narrative) on EOL experiences and communication, which allowed for the measurement of the difference from the baseline scores of the training sessions. The nurses narratively described their awareness of the patient/family life experience and how they would incorporate their new knowledge into their practice of helping patients make decisions.

The fourth stage, Act, involved making a decision about the next steps based on the project results and planning for changes in the next cycle or further implementation to continue to sustain the positive changes in communication among hospice nurses, patients, and caregivers. In this stage, a report of the training outcomes was shared with CCH stakeholders. The author of the project discussed the next steps with the CCH stakeholders regarding additional changes that were needed to ensure sustainability.

Literature Review

A literature search was conducted using several databases that included Google Scholar, CINAHL, PubMed Medline, and PubMed. In addition, resources in the Institute for Healthcare Improvement and the Agency for Healthcare Quality and Research were reviewed and added to the literature review. The search targeted published resources from 2000 to 2019. A number of search terms were used including "hospice nursing education," "palliative care," "end-of-life care," "hospice care," "palliative care demand," "end-of-life communication," "comfort care," "advance care planning," "advance directives," "death anxiety," "caregivers' knowledge and anxiety," and "communication avoidance." In addition, the reference section of selected articles was reviewed to obtain further research articles on the topic. The articles were selected based on their relevance from the titles and abstracts. Only full-text articles in English were selected. Appendix B summarizes the literature search process and shows the number of studies that were reviewed for this project.

In the following sections, an overview of the literature related to EOL care in nursing is presented, followed by the main findings relevant to communication at EOL and findings in the literature evaluating the use of the ELNEC Module 6 Communication and COMFORTTMSM training

Hospice Nursing and End of Life Care

The role of the hospice nurse is to provide direct patient care (Fairbrother & Paice, 2005) and build a strong relationship with patients and their families to help them facilitate their goals and wishes for EOL. Unfortunately, several gaps were identified in the literature, which indicates certain aspects of nursing education and institution-based continuing education regarding EOL care are lacking (Whitehead et al., 2010). The educational gaps contribute to a lack of knowledge

of and comfort with conversations that should occur at the EOL (Beresford et al., 2002; Black & Emmet, 2006; Dugan, 2009; Finnerty & Gregory, 2010; Friesen & Andersen, 2019; Jezewski et al., 2007; Kortess-Miller et al., 2007; Phillip et al., 2008; Whitehead et al., 2010).

Hospice nurses who experience difficulty in communicating with EOL patients and families typically lack training in the communication skills needed for this population. This lack of educational training makes it difficult to manage and support patients and their families during the EOL transition (Gagnon & Duggleby, 2014; Malloy et al., 2010). Lee et al. (2018) identified that less experienced nurses have high levels of anxiety and report a lack of communication skills as a significant barrier to providing EOL care. The integration of communication skills training could lessen burnout and staff turnover by providing the needed support and skills to care for a growing and challenging patient population experiencing EOL. (Lee et al., 2018)

Hospice nurses are in a better position to provide EOL care than any other type of healthcare professional (Barrere & Durkin, 2013; Malloy et al., 2010; White & Coyne, 2011). The IOM stated in their landmark report, *Approaching Death: Improving Care at the EOL*, that patients with advanced chronic illnesses should receive competent care (Kuehn, 2010). White and Coyne (2011) indicated that nurses reported they believe EOL care was part of the care they provided as nurses. Nurses believed that continuous training was essential to ensure that they could provide this care as their patients transitioned in their health status. Hospice nurses have reported concerns regarding their communication skills with patients and families at EOL. In a survey of nurses, it was reported that 89% believed that EOL content was an essential component in nursing education. However, 62% rated their undergraduate preparation on this topic as inadequate (Ferrell et al., 2005). The amount and quality of continuing education that nurses receive determines the highest quality of care that is provided to patients and their families at the

EOL (White et al., 2012). Some researchers have stated that nurses feel less competent or confident in implementing EOL care due to their poor communication skills. They feel that they are not well trained. Thus, there has been a focus in the United States to increase nurses' expertise in EOL care via the ELNEC standardized curriculum (White & Coyne, 2011; Mazanec et al., 2017).

Multiple studies have shown that there is a gap in EOL education, leading to a lack of comfort among nurses in providing EOL communication and care (Malloy et al., 2010; McCourt et al., 2013). The City of Hope (2015) identified a gap in EOL care and developed the ELNEC program as a means to address that need. Although there has been research conducted in the area of EOL education from 1984 to 2012, regarding best practices for curriculum development for nursing students, the ELNEC program was the first to design a specific and comprehensive educational curriculum. (Gillan et al., 2014).

There have been several research studies on the ELNEC program. Malloy et al. (2010) surveyed 333 nurses who attended an ELNEC conference and analyzed the responses of those participants who expressed concerns regarding the challenges of communication with EOL patients. Malloy et al. (2010) found that there was a need for future research and education to enhance nurses' abilities to communicate effectively and compassionately during EOL. There were several areas in need of improvement related to communication. The most challenging areas of communication include discussing bad news, talking with physicians about palliative care issues, discussing spiritual concerns, and talking with patients /families from different cultures (Malloy et al., 2010).

Additionally, it was noted that education regarding communication skills in EOL care is needed for first-year nurses and graduate nurses as well as continuing education for practicing

nurses (Malloy, et al., 2010). Likewise, White and Coyne (2011) indicated that EOL education was essential for practicing nurses who work in hospice or palliative care. They found that communication skills were foundational to the practice of nursing.

Caregivers perform a vital role in the care of their loved ones with disabilities and severe illness, which includes end-of-life (EOL) care. Existing evidence suggests that EOL care can be stressful for caregivers (Ornstein et al., 2017). This stress is derived from the difficult decisions caregivers must make, as well as watching their loved ones die (Ornstein et al., 2017). As a result of this stress, caregivers experience high levels of depression and anxiety in caring for their loved ones during EOL care (Ornstein et al., 2017).

Abbot et al. (2014), Kramer and Boelk (2015), Krug et al. (2016), and Wen et al. (2018) conducted observational studies of family caregivers at EOL. All four studies were similar in identifying the caregiver's burden in providing QOL for their loved one. They also reported that caregivers often experience depressive symptoms, have suicidal ideation, and lack communication skills in delivering EOL care for their terminally ill family members. The samples were small in each study ranging from 100 to 125 participants, with an age range of 58 to 80; all were adult caregivers, mostly female. The participants in these studies were mostly caring for a family member with advanced cancer. The studies demonstrated that regular screening and assessment of caregiver needs were associated with improvement in reducing the caregivers' level of distress, improved ability of nurses and caregivers/families to communicate more openly, and increased participation in shared decision-making with other family members. Hospice nurses' regular assessment and open communication with the caregivers helped avoid family conflicts, increased the patient's and caregivers' knowledge regarding the management of

their symptoms, and reduced suicidal ideation by providing information and resources (Abbott et al., 2014).

Hospice nurses may have difficulty communicating with patients and their families due to inadequate communication skills, which can create role challenges for the caregivers in their ability to be supportive of their loved one (Bullington et al., 2019; Wittenberg-Lyles et al., 2010a). There are continual demands placed on caregivers, which require expert information, attentive communication, and access to resources, which ELNEC trained nurses can provide (Wittenberg-Lyles et al., 2010a).

Communication

Communication skills are paramount in the effective delivery of EOL and palliative care. Healthcare providers, especially nurses, play a key role in assisting patients and their families in establishing goals of care (Malloy et al., 2010). A terminal illness is a family experience. Nurses with effective communication skills can identify important tasks, barriers to positive communication, and family issues that create discussions for caregivers to have with a loved one. Nurses need to improve their communication skills in providing care to their EOL patients and families. Often in EOL situations, the emphasis has been on physician communication and largely focused on the singular topic of "breaking bad news." There has been less emphasis on communication as a vital skill for nurses (Malloy et al., 2010). Therefore, nurses should be trained so they can provide opportunities for patients to explore their concerns, talk about their need for independence, and to maintain a sense of control.

Communication is more than just answering questions about disease and prognosis; it involves establishing trust. Communication helps build a partnership among patients, families, and caregivers that is integral to the practice of palliative/hospice care. Communication occurs

through the spoken words, inaction, and in silence. Thus, the ability to practice positive communication is an essential tool to support patients and caregivers. The principle of communication is enhanced by certain nurse behaviors, both nonverbal and verbal (Boreale, 2017; Dahlin & Wittenberg, 2019). It is noted that 80% of communication is nonverbal, which includes body language, presence, tone of voice, and mannerism (Boreale, 2017; Dahlin & Wittenberg, 2019). Another form of communication is attentive listening and having a mindful presence. Mindful presence involves being nonverbally present for the patient and family while being attentive, non-judgmental, and empathic (Wittenberg-Lyles et al., 2013). This form of communication is required in hospice care, and communication training is crucial for hospice nurses. Lack of communication in hospice nursing care results in many patients not having a "good death." The type and quality of continuing education activities are critical factors that need to be considered and are necessary to ensure that nurses receive the best possible training in providing high-quality EOL patient care (White et al., 2012).

Malloy et al. (2010) state communication is a cornerstone of basic nursing practice and is a fundamental skill required across all settings of care. In the field of palliative/hospice care, recent literature has emphasized the role of medicine in "breaking bad news" with much less emphasis on the role of nursing in supporting patients and families after bad news has been received, throughout their illness, and until the time of death (Malloy et al., 2014). Malloy et al. (2010) provided patient narratives that demonstrated powerful and emotional accounts of nurses' experiences. For example, one narrative would include a hospice nurse's story of a patient's imminent death: "His respiratory rate was labored, like in the 60s, and I just knew he was dying. There was no doubt about it, he went into Cheyne-Stokes, and maybe 10 minutes later, he died." The nurse went on to explain the death of the patient to the family by saying: "I went in and

said, 'His heart stopped beating.' I didn't say he was gone or that he passed. I think I said, 'His heart gave out' or 'his heart isn't beating anymore' or something to that effect." (Mitchell et al., 2006) This scenario demonstrates an example of a nurse whose communication style with the family was poor, nonemphatic, and matter of fact. She should have used more kind words and told the family he was gone or say he passed away. The nurse's experience illustrated the need for improvement in communication skills, given the difficult conversations nurses have with EOL patients and families. The ELNEC curriculum is pertinent to EOL care because it focuses on developing interpersonal competence to provide compassionate care. The guidelines of the ACCN states that "a nurse must have, among other skills, effective and compassionate communication abilities when death issues are a concern" (Mitchell et al., 2006).

ELNEC and COMFORT Training

ELNEC Training

The ELNEC program was funded by the Robert Wood Johnson Foundation (Wallace et al., 2009) and was developed at City of Hope National Medical Center in collaboration with the American Association of College of Nursing (AACN). The program is designed to improve EOL care by healthcare providers. The ELNEC program identifies recommended competencies and curricular guidelines for evidence based EOL nursing care (AACN, 2004; 2015; ELNEC, 2012b; Virani & Sofer, 2003). The topics addressed in the ELNEC program include pain and symptom management, ethical/legal issues, cultural considerations at EOL, communication, grief, and bereavement, and care at the time of death (AACN, 2004; ELNEC, 2012b).

The ELNEC program has a long history of providing formal training for nurses in palliative and EOL care. As of 2016, about 615 000 of the three million registered nurses in the United States had participated in the ELNEC courses (Glover et al., 2017). Despite these

commendable efforts, the healthcare system has a long way to go in ensuring access to patient-centered care at the EOL (Glover et al., 2017). The use of the ELNEC curriculum by practicing nurses within the hospice care environment has improved their communication skills with patients and families (Matzo et al., 2003). Communication is vital in all healthcare situations but is of paramount significance at the EOL. The ELNEC Module 6 Communication reviews the dimensions and importance of communication during EOL care. It presents the complexities of communicating with patients and families and offers specific communication techniques to be used by the healthcare providers. For example, it includes the following aspects of communication training: discussing pain management and treatment of other frequent symptoms seen at EOL, understanding illness trajectory at EOL, resolving conflicts, and engaging in patient, family, and provider partnership in EOL care (Wittenberg-Lyles et al., 2010; 2013; Matzo et al., 2003).

Wittenberg-Lyles et al. (2010b; 2013) conducted a study to evaluate the pre- and post-knowledge attainment of nursing students enrolled in the ELNEC Communication Module. They found that nursing students improved their communication skills associated with EOL care (Wittenberg-Lyles et al., 2013). The content addressed in the communication module included the nature of skillful communication, the importance of strong interprofessional collaboration; the importance of verbal and nonverbal communication; and the importance of offering presence while actively listening to the patient and family (Wittenberg-Lyles et al., 2013). The ELNEC educational strategies included interactive teaching methods, group discussion, case studies, storytelling, and pictures (Robinson, 2004; Behr, 2014; Wittenberg-Lyles et al., 2013). ELNEC is a universally recognized course that is updated frequently when new research becomes available (Dahlin & Wittenberg, 2019). Currently, ELNEC is the only formalized

communication curriculum focusing on EOL and hospice care issues that is available in the United States. The ELNEC course is a method of increasing nurses' knowledge about the end of life (Bodine, 2016). Research supports the use of the ELNEC curriculum for EOL education. Educating practicing nurses about EOL is an effective mechanism for both increasing knowledge and improving attitudes (O'Shea & Mager, 2019).

COMFORT^{TMSM} Training

The COMFORT^{TMSM} Communication Curriculum is a national health communication curriculum developed and offered by the City of Hope (COH) through its Division of Nursing Research and Education. It is intended to improve communication of nurses with oncology patients and in healthcare situations in general. The COMFORT^{TMSM} Communication Curriculum was funded by grants from the National Cancer Institute, the Archstone Foundation, and the Stupski Foundation, and provides information about essential communication skills and strategies to enhance awareness about relational communication and ability to provide compassionate nursing care at the EOL (Lee et al., 2018; Paice et al., 2006). COMFORT is an acronym, which stands for the seven training modules for teaching the skills of communication (Wittenberg et al., 2018). These seven modules include:

C- Communication (narrative practice) Module C – uses communication tools, which focus on helping nurses to identify the difference between a task and relational communication. It discusses how nurses can engage in a narrative practice that aims to learn the patient/family story and uses that strategy and integrates the story into the information giving for patients and families.

O- Orientation & Options. Module O/O – emphasizes the importance of using plain language with short sentences when communicating with patients and families and when

providing information regarding their diseases and management at EOL. The patients' and family's cultural and social backgrounds are important aspects of communicating related to literacy needs and cultural beliefs.

M- Mindful Communication Module M - involves being aware of how you and others respond, avoiding judgment, and adapting nonverbal communication to convey support and empathy.

F- Family Caregivers Module F – involves determining the literacy-level, family support system, and presence of family conflicts in order to maintain contact with a key family spokesperson, and engage family members in family meetings to help clarify goals of care for their loved one.

O- Openings Module O- focuses on providing patients/families an opportunity to open a conversation and sharing their feeling. The opening of a conversation with a patient allows the nurse an opportunity to address QOL care questions. A nurse can use a technique called ACT, which is an acronym for: (A - Acknowledge feelings; C - Comments on their feeling being similar to other patients in EOL situations, T - talk about QOL and values). This technique helps to build rapport and engage in open discussion.

R- Relating Module R – helps the nurse understand that communication involves the understanding that the way things are said will impact the way words are received and interpreted.

T- Team Module T – explains that caring for a patient at the EOL is a team approach that requires team communication (Lin et al., 2018). This is necessary to deliver holistic, patient-centered care. Effective communication and respect among interdisciplinary teams and nurses

will bring positive experiences. Team-based communication should be collaborative, productive, and frequent.

The COMFORT training provides an easy -to- use method of teaching communication skills. Researchers found that COMFORT training positively impacted student attitudes, perceptions, and self-efficacy in communicating with patients and families ($P < .052$) (Goldsmith et al., 2015; Wittenberg-Lyles et al., 2013). Nurses' positive responses to the curriculum indicated effectiveness of COMFORT training for nurses.

Summary

Overall, the literature supported that nurses play a critical role in EOL care; however, preparation and training for nurses during their educational programs have been inconsistent (Corcoran, 2016). Communication is the foundation of excellent palliative/hospice care. It is helpful to understand communication techniques, especially when speaking with seriously ill patients and their families (Malloy et al., 2010). The ELNEC communication program reviews dimensions of communication, which emphasize the importance of excellent communication in EOL care that requires complex conversations with patients and families. The ELNEC offers specific communication techniques that are effective in helping to build connections with patients and their families. The ELNEC training helps with communicating bad news and initiating discussions of advance care planning and end care goals with patients and families. The behavior of healthcare professionals can influence communication outcomes, both verbally and nonverbally (O'Shea & Mager, 2019; Dahlin & Wittenberg, 2019).

Methods

The project aimed to improve the communication skills of CCH nurses using ELNEC communication materials/modules. The method section provides a discussion of the project design, setting, participants, ethical issues, planning, instruments and interventions that were used in this DNP project to address communication strategies during EOL care. In addition, it includes an evaluation plan to determine the effectiveness of the ELNEC training (Paice et al., 2008). The hospice nurses at the project setting identified a concern regarding their comfort level in communicating about the EOL with their patients and families. They perceived their communication skills as insufficient to meet the needs of their EOL patients.

This project focused on answering three quality improvement evaluation questions. The first question was, "Did participation in the communication training program improve the hospice nurses' knowledge and skills relevant to communication?" The second question was, "What communication areas improved the most?" And the third question was, "How satisfied were the nurses with the content and activities of the communication training program?"

Design

The project involved a quality improvement utilizing the PDSA model. The project utilized pre- and post-testing of knowledge and self-efficacy. A pre- and post-assessment of participants' perceptions of their self-efficacy in communication related to ELNEC knowledge and skills among hospice nurses employed a Likert scale response set. The pre-assessment of knowledge provided the baseline assessment of nurses' knowledge of the ELNEC communication content, and the post-assessment consisted of the knowledge gained after participation in the ELNEC program.

Sample

The sample included all the nurses at CCH. There were nine nurses of whom seven delivered direct patient care, one nurse was a manager, and another was the director. Although the ELNEC training was voluntary, all the participants gave consent to participate in the ELNEC training by attending the sessions. Participants received continuing education contact hours for their attendance from CCH. The Director of the facility informed nurses of the training sessions at their monthly meeting and by email. A sign-in sheet was used to track attendance of the training.

Setting

This quality improvement project took place at a community care hospice facility located in Southern California. The facility is under the purview of the Centers for Medicare and Medicaid Services (CMS) and has provided services to the community for the past 17 years. This facility provides home hospice care to an average of 210 patients annually who have less than six months to live.

Procedures***Training Course***

The training utilized an interactive approach in combination with PowerPoint lectures, case studies, small group discussions, and narrative practice (Wittenberg-Lyles et al., 2013). The education was provided through a training workshop that focused on EOL communication. The content of the training was based on the communication modules from ELNEC (i.e. Module 6) and COMFORT^{TMSM} material. The training was delivered through face-to-face sessions conducted based on the facility's COVID-19 pandemic guidelines enforcing social distancing (six feet apart), face mask wearing, handwashing and use of hand sanitizers. The training was

conducted using PowerPoint presentations, small group discussion, case studies, and narrative engagements of the nurses using case studies relevant to their hospice practice. Pre- and post-assessment tools were distributed to the participated hospice nurses who attended the training. Assessment of the nurses' ELNEC knowledge and communication skills was conducted using pre- and post- questionnaires. The ELNEC and COMFORT module outlines are depicted in Appendix C1 (ELNEC) and Appendix C2 (COMFORT). The lesson plan with the topic and activities for each session was outlined upon discussion with the facility Director (see Appendices D1, D2, D3, and D4). The training was done in two-hour sessions every two weeks for one month at the CCH center for a total of two sessions.

Data Collection

The collection of baseline data occurred immediately before commencement of the training and after the training. The following data were collected at baseline: Nurses' demographics (6 items), items generated by the project author, nurses' knowledge of EOL communication at baseline and post-implementation (14 items), and nurses' perceived self-efficacy with conducting EOL conversations at baseline and post-implementation with patients/families (10 items).

Outcomes Measures

Four tools were used in this project to assess nurses' knowledge and skills relevant to EOL communication. All four tools were adapted from ELNEC except for the demographic questionnaire. They included the following:

Demographics data questionnaire: This tool assessed the nurses' demographic characteristics with six items generated by the project author. This questionnaire was administered at baseline. The items solicited information about nurses' previous hospice care

experience, age, gender, and highest education level. Appendix E shows the Demographics questionnaire.

Nurses' Knowledge of EOL Communication

Nurses' knowledge was assessed using a modified tool from ELNEC. This tool consisted of 13 multiple-choice items, which was assessed by the number of correct responses at the baseline and post-implementation. In addition, input from nurses was solicited in one question (labeled as Question 14) that asked nurses to reflect on the EOL care narratively—scale modified from that of the ELNEC tools. The multiple-choice score ranged from a low of one to a high of 13. A higher score indicated a higher level of communication knowledge and ability to communicate effectively. The nurses' performance on this tool was divided into five levels of knowledge: 100% - 90% very knowledgeable (5); 89% - 80% knowledgeable (4); 79% - 70% neutral (3); 69% - 60% poor level of knowledge (2); and $\leq 59\%$ deficit (1). The Nurses' Knowledge of EOL tool is shown in Appendix F1.

Nurses' Perceived Self-Efficacy

Nurses' perceived self-efficacy with conducting difficult EOL conversations with patients and families was assessed using a modified 10-item survey which is scored on a five-point Likert scale. The Likert scores were interpreted as follows in this project. (1= not difficult; 2 = somewhat difficult; 3=neutral, 4= difficult; 5= very difficult). Nurses' Perceived Self-efficacy tool is shown in Appendix F2.

Nurses Evaluation of Communication Training

A seven items tool scored on a 5-point Likert scale (1= strongly disagree; 2=disagree; 3= neutral, 4 = agree; 5= strongly agree) was used to assess nurses' evaluation of the training and was administered post-implementation. This tool was used in ELNEC programs and was used in

this project as it was originally designed. The Evaluation of Communication tool is presented in Appendix G. The project author obtained a written permission from the ELNEC authors to use their tools in this project (Appendices H, I, and J).

Analysis and Evaluation Plan

Descriptive statistics were used to describe the demographic data of the project's participants. The number of correct answers was compared between nurses' responses on the pre and posttest. The percent change was used to indicate effectiveness of the educational training. The change in Nurses' Perceived Self-Efficacy scores was compared between pre and post training using the mean score change. Descriptive statistics were used to describe the nurses' evaluation of the communication educational training. Finally, percentages and overall mean scores were used to evaluate the nurses' perceptions of the benefits of the communication training. Data were analyzed using descriptive statistics because of the small sample size. Results were displayed using BAR tables.

Ethical Considerations

Permission to conduct the project was obtained from the CCH Director, shown in Appendix K. The project was submitted to the Institutional Review Board (IRB) at California State University, Long Beach, to ensure the project followed ethical guidelines and was approved (Appendix L). This project involved hospice nurses and did not involve any patients or families. The data collected from the CCH nurses were confidential and secured in a password-protected computer that was accessed by the project author only (Appendix M). The project author was employed part-time at the project facility.

Results

The purpose of this quality improvement (QI) project was to initiate, implement, and evaluate an educational program that used the national communication training modules (namely ELNEC Module 6 Communication and the COMFORT ^{TMSM} curriculum) for hospice nurses at a Community Care Hospice (CCH), who provided support to patients and their caregivers during EOL. All statistical analyses were performed using Intellectus Statistics.

Two-tailed paired t-Tests pre-total and post-total knowledge acquisition and self-efficacy were calculated. In addition, mean scores and standard deviations were calculated for each of the 13 knowledge questions as a score of one was given for a correct answer and a score of 0 was given if the answer was incorrect.

Characteristics of Nurse Participants

There were nine nurses who participated in the educational program. Eight (88.9%) nurses were female, and one was male (11.1%). The racial and ethnic makeup of the participants were White-Hispanics ($n= 4$, 44.4%), Asia/Pacific Islanders ($n=4$, 44.4%), and Native American ($n=1$, 11.11%). Almost all participants were above the age of 35 ($n=8$, 89%). Four of the nurses in the project were prepared at the RN Diploma level (44.4%). Table 1 shows the detailed demographics.

Table 1

Participant Demographic Characteristics

Variable	N	%
Gender		
Female	8	88.89
Male	1	11.11
Race/Ethnicity		
White Non-Hispanic	1	11.11

Native America	0	0
White Hispanic	4	44.44
African America	0	0
Asia Pacific Islander	4	44.44
Level of Education		
Diploma R.N. (1)	4	44.4
Undergraduate BSN (2)	2	22.2
Graduate MSN (3)	2	22.2
Other ADN (4)	1	11.1

The average age in the sample was 23.78 ($SD = 17.31$, Min = 6, Max = 50) years of nursing experience. The participants were an experienced group with a mean length of time in nursing of six to 50 years and were from diverse practice settings. The years of hospice experiences ranged from just under one year to 26 years with an average of 10 years ($SD = 10.9$). The summary statistics can be found in Table 2.

Table 2

Years of Experience in Nursing and Hospice Care

Variable	<i>M</i>	<i>SD</i>	<i>N</i>	<i>SEM</i>	Min	Max
Years of Nursing Experience	23.78	17.31	9	5.77	6.00	50.00
1-26 Years of Hospice Care	10.00	10.90	9	3.63	0.00	26.00

Nurses' Knowledge of EOL Communication

Percent of correct test items was calculated for the pre and posttest knowledge items. The average percent correct score for the pretest was 72.62% ($SD = 7.81$, $SEM = 2.60$, Min = 61.50, Max = 84.6). The post questionnaire had an average of 92.30% ($SD = 9.43$, $SEM = 3.14$, Min = 69.20, Max = 100.00). The level of knowledge in communication skills and, thus, the ability to communicate effectively was categorized into five levels based on the percent of correct knowledge scores pre -and post-tesing. The mean percent scores of the pre and posttests were

given a rating of one to 5: 100% - 90% very knowledgeable (5), 89% - 80% knowledgeable (4) : 79% – 70% neutral (3); 69% - 60% poor level of knowledge (2); and $\leq 59\%$ deficit (1). The pretest level of knowledge had an average level score 2.67 ($SD = 0.71$, $SE_M = 0.24$, Min = 2.00, Max = 4.00) indicating a level of poor knowledge. The posttest level of knowledge had an average level of knowledge score of 4.67 ($SD = 1.00$, Min = 2.00, Max = 5.00), indicating very knowledgeable (see Table 3). Bar plots of the mean pre and posttest percent scores and the average pre and posttest level of knowledge are shown in Figures 1 and 2, respectively.

Table 3

Pre- and Posttest Mean Percent Score and Pre and Posttest Average Level of Knowledge

Variable	<i>M</i>	<i>SD</i>	<i>n</i>	<i>SE_M</i>	Min	Max
Pretest Percent	72.78	7.76	9	2.59	62.00	85.00
Posttest Percent	92.11	9.49	9	3.16	69.00	100.00
Pretest Knowledge Level	2.67	0.71	9	0.24	2.00	4.00
Posttest Knowledge Level	4.67	1.00	9	0.33	2.00	5.00

Figure 1

Mean Percent of Pretest and Posttest Knowledge Scores

Figure 2*Mean Pretest and Posttest Knowledge Levels***Two-Tailed Paired Sample *t*-Test for Knowledge Acquisition**

A two-tailed paired samples *t*-test was conducted to examine whether the mean differences of the total scores of pretest and post-test of knowledge were significantly different. A Shapiro-Wilk test was conducted to determine normalcy, and a Levene's test was conducted to assess the homogeneity of variance. The result of the two-tailed paired samples *t*-test was significant. The percent mean of the pretest was significantly lower than the percent mean of posttest, indicating that knowledge improved in the posttest. The results are presented in Table 4.

Table 4

*Two-Tailed Paired Samples *t*-Test for the Difference Between Pretest and Posttest Total Knowledge Percent Scores*

Pretest Percent		Posttest Percent		<i>T</i>	<i>P</i>	<i>D</i>
<i>M</i>	<i>SD</i>	<i>M</i>	<i>SD</i>			
72.62	7.81	92.30	9.43	-6.20	< .001	2.07

Note. N = 9. Degrees of Freedom for the *t*-statistic = 8. *d* represents Cohen's *d*.

Comparison of Mean Scores of the 13 Individual Pre and Post Knowledge Questions

Summary statistics were calculated for pre-test and post-test for each of the 13 questions (Questions in Appendix E) regarding nurses' knowledge on EOL communication. A comparison was made between the mean scores for each of the 13 pre- and post-questions. Ten questions showed an increase in nurses' knowledge: Question one, resolving conflict; Question two, describing emotions; Question three, effective communication techniques; Question four, mindful presence; Question six, family meeting; Question seven, discussing the diagnosis; Question eight, facilitating EOL decisions; Question 10, communication myths; Question 12, sorry vs. wish; and Question 13, patient's beliefs. Three questions showed no change in knowledge as they were answered correctly on both pre and post testing. They were question numbers five (opening communication process), nine (expectations of hospice nurses), and 11 (communicating with family members). Overall, the results showed an increase in knowledge among the nurses who participated in the EOL communication program (Table 5).

Table 5

Summary Statistics: Comparison of Pre- and Posttest Individual Knowledge Question Scores

Variable	Pretest			Posttest		
	<i>M</i>	<i>SD</i>	<i>SE_M</i>	<i>M</i>	<i>SD</i>	<i>SE_M</i>
1. Conflict	0.56	0.53	0.18	0.89	0.33	0.11
2. Emotions	0.22	0.44	0.15	0.67	0.50	0.17
3. Communication	0.89	0.33	0.11	1.00	0.00	0.00
4. Mindful presence	0.89	0.33	0.11	1.00	0.00	0.00
5. Open communication	1.00	0.00	0.00	1.00	0.00	0.00
6. Family meetings	0.67	0.50	0.17	1.00	0.00	0.00
7. Diagnosis discussion	0.44	0.53	0.18	0.89	0.33	0.11

8. EOL talks	0.89	0.33	0.11	1.00	0.00	0.00
9. Expectations	1.00	0.00	0.00	1.00	0.00	0.00
10. Myths	0.56	0.53	0.18	0.89	0.33	0.11
11. Communicate with family	1.00	0.00	0.00	1.00	0.00	0.00
12. Sorry vs wish	0.56	0.53	0.18	0.67	0.50	0.17
13. Patient beliefs	0.78	0.44	0.15	1.00	0.00	0.00

Responses to Question 14 by Nurses: Reflection Regarding Communication at EOL

At the beginning of the first educational session, the majority of hospice nurses indicated that the most challenging areas were communicating with patients and families regarding EOL care. Nurses found it difficult to talk to patients and families after receiving bad news, and talking about hospice care issues, burden of care or religious/spiritual issues. However, after the ELNEC and COMFORT training, participants recognized that communicating with patients and families at the EOL is vital and helps patients understand their pain and symptoms, spiritual needs, and decision-making at the EOL. Nurses expressed that after their training they felt more comfortable communicating with patients and families. A few nurses expressed feeling comfortable listening, maintaining eye contact, holding a patient's hand in support, and allowing patients to express their pain and symptoms. In addition, the training brought confidence in the nurses' communication skills regarding EOL and talking about the burden of care and feeling they were now better able to assist patients and families. Themes of pain and symptoms, spiritual needs, death, suffering, and burden on loved ones emerged based on the participant responses to Question 14 (See Table 6). A summary of the individual narrative question 14, a reflection regarding communication at EOL, can be found in Appendix O.

Table 6

Grouping of Narrative Questions: Reflection Regarding Communication at EOL/ Responses from Participants (n=9)

Pre-Questions Responses	Post-Questions Responses
Pain and Symptoms	
N1, N3, N7, N8, N9 - No responses N2, N5 - Every family is different in coping with pain, which needs to assess during pain and discussion with the family. N4, N6 – Comfort patient by listening, eye contact, holding hand, and patient to express their pain and symptoms.	N7, N9 - No responses N1, N2, N8 - After communication training, I feel comfortable talking to patients and families/caregivers. N3, N5, N6 - Feel comfortable talking to patients and families/caregivers. N4 - Avoid oral sedation, feel comfortable talking to patient and family.
Spiritual Needs and /or Concerns About Suffering and /or Death	
N1, N2, N3, N7, N8, N9 - No response N4 - Anxiety talking about spiritual and death. N5 - Tend to differ from spiritual care (resources) N6 - Offer priest or chaplain to visit	N1, N3, N8 - Comfortable talking about spirituality. N2, N5, N6 - Feel uncomfortable talking about spirituality; usually call the chaplain. N4 - Anxiety talking about death and spirituality is personal -priest or chaplain should be involved. N7, N9 - No response
Burden of Care or Strain Loved Ones May Experience	
N1, N2, N3, N7, N8, N9 - No Response N4 - Providing the gift of staying home. N5 - Talk about options N6 - Increase pain relief medication and provide support.	N1, N2, N6, N8 - After the training, feel comfortable to talk about the burden of care. N3, N4 - Able to assist comfortably. N5 - Option of care and resources N7, N9 - No response

N= Nurse

Nurses' Perceptions of Self-Efficacy in Communications with Patients

Self-efficacy (confidence) in communication skill level pre-total scores averaged 22 ($SD = 10.01$, $SE_M = 3.34$) with a post-total average of 14.56 ($SD = 3.64$, $SE_M = 1.21$) (See Figure 3).

Responses to the Likert scale were such that higher scores meant lower perceived self-efficacy,

and vice versa. The findings demonstrated that the participants' perception of self-efficacy improved after receiving the EOL communication training. Thus, scores of one or two in the posttest indicated the participants experienced increased confidence (self-efficacy) in their ability to communicate – communication was not difficult or only somewhat difficult. Higher scores of four and five indicated greater level of difficulty (less confidence) in communication (see Table 7).

Figure 3

Mean Scores of Pre- and Posttests of Self-Efficacy

Table 7

Summary Statistics for Self-Efficacy Pre-and Post-Total Scores

Variable	<i>M</i>	<i>SD</i>	<i>N</i>	<i>SE_M</i>	Min	Max
Pre-Total	22.00	10.01	9	3.34	10.00	43.00
Post-Total	14.56	3.64	9	1.21	10.00	22.00

Two-Tailed Paired Sample *t*-Test for Self-Efficacy in Patient Communication

A two-tailed paired samples *t*-test was conducted to examine whether the mean difference between the self-efficacy pre-total and post-total scores was significantly statistically different. A Shapiro-Wilk test was conducted to determine normalcy, and a Levene's test was conducted to assess the homogeneity of variance. This was to determine whether the variance between the pre-total and post-total was significantly different. The result of the two-tailed paired samples *t*-Test was significant, indicating that the difference in the mean between pre-total and post-total mean was significantly different. The mean of the pre-total was significantly higher than the mean for the post-total. A lower score represents a higher perception of one's self-efficacy in communicating about EOL issues with patients and their families. The results are presented in Table 8. A bar plot of the means is shown in Figure 2.

Table 8

Two-Tailed Paired Samples t-Test Self-efficacy for the Difference Between Pre-TOTAL and Post-TOTAL

Pre-Total		Post-Total		<i>T</i>	<i>p</i>	<i>D</i>
<i>M</i>	<i>SD</i>	<i>M</i>	<i>SD</i>			
22.00	10.01	14.56	3.64	3.41	.009	1.14

Note. N = 9. Degrees of Freedom for the *t*-statistic = 8. *d* represents Cohen's *d*.

Comparison of the Mean Scores of the Pre- and Post- Self-Efficacy Items

A two-tailed paired samples *t*-Test was conducted to examine whether the mean difference of each of the ten questions for the pre- and post self-efficacy test was significantly different. Summary statistics were calculated for pretest and posttest questions to conduct a paired comparison between the mean scores, with an alpha (0.05) based value for each of the ten pre-and post-questions (See Table 8). The findings suggest there was a difference in the mean of

the pre- and post-tests of six self-efficacy questions that were significantly different. The two-tailed paired samples *t*-Test for pre and post on six questions that were significant, based on an alpha value of 0.05, were talking with patients once they had bad news (Q1), talking with family members of seriously ill patients (Q2), talking with patients/families about spiritual concerns (Q3), discussing decisions such as advance directives (Q4), talking with patients or families about suffering (Q8), and talking with nurse colleagues about hospice care issues (Q9). The difference between pre and posttest scores of the remaining questions were not statistically significant. See Table 8 for details.

Overall, the results showed a significant increase in self-efficacy after completion of the EOL communication training. The results are presented in Table 9.

Table 9

Two-Tailed Paired Samples t-Test for Pre/Post Nurses' Self-Efficacy

Q	Difficulty of Conversation	Pre-Q		Post Q		T	P	D
		M	SD	M	SD			
1	Talking with patients once they had bad news	3.0	1.32	1.78	.44	3.35	.010*	1.12
2	Talking with family members of seriously ill patients	2.44	1.24	1.67	0.50	2.40	.043*	0.80
3	Talking with patients/families about spiritual concerns	2.56	1.13	1.44	0.53	3.59	.007*	1.20
4	Discussing decision such as advance directive, DNR	2.22	0.97	1.44	0.53	2.80	.023*	0.93
5	Remaining silent and listening to painful feelings from patients and /families	1.89	1.54	1.11	0.33	1.79	.111	0.60
6	Talking with patients or families from different culture	2.11	1.27	1.56	0.53	1.89	.095	0.63
8	Talking with patients or families about suffering	2.67	1.41	1.89	1.05	3.50	.008*	1.17
9	Talking with nurse colleagues about hospice care issues	1.89	1.17	1.44	0.73	2.53	.035*	0.84
10	Talking with families about pain and symptoms	1.67	1.32	1.22	0.44	1.32	.225	0.44

Note. N = 9. Degrees of Freedom for the *t*-statistics = 8. *d* represents Cohen's *d*; Communication Survey 5-Point Likert Scale (Scale from 0+ (not difficult to 5 = (Very difficult). Q = question: * < .05.

Evaluation of Nurses Satisfaction with EOL Communication Training

A Likert scale was used to evaluate the nurses' satisfaction with the communication training using a one-to-five-point satisfaction scale: 1- strongly disagree (strongly dissatisfied with the training); 2 - disagree (not satisfied with the training); 3 - neutral (did not disagree or agree); 4 – agrees (satisfied with the training); and 5 - strongly agree (strongly satisfied with the training). The mean and standard deviation scores for each of the seven questions were calculated and displayed in Table 10.

Three questions had mean scores of 4 or higher. Scores for question 1 (Do you think the ELNEC Module 6 Communication and COMFORT curriculum improved your knowledge concerning the principles of hospice care?), question 6 (The activities/interactions and resources enhanced the effectiveness of this activity), and question 7 (Do you plan on using what you have learned from the ELNEC Module 6 Communication and COMFORT curriculum, open-ended, in your workplace, Hospice care) were 4.00 (*SD*, 0.50), 4.22 (*SD*, 0.67), and 4.56 (*SD*, 0.73), respectively. The other four questions had means scores that ranged from 3.56 to 3.78, and their standard deviations ranged from 0.50 to 0.83. Question four scored the lowest (3.56, *SD* 0.53); question seven was the highest (4.56, *SD* 0.73) mean scoring questions and had the wider standard deviation score. The results are presented in Table 10

Table 10

Summary Statistics Evaluation of Communication Training

Variable	<i>M</i>	<i>SD</i>	<i>N</i>	<i>SE_M</i>	Min	Max
1. ELNEC/Comfort hospice principles	4.00	0.50	9	0.17	3.00	5.00
2. ELNEC/Comfort EOL principles	3.78	0.67	9	0.22	3.00	5.00
3. Communication with patients and families	3.78	0.83	9	0.28	3.00	5.00

4. Cultural issues in EOL	3.56	0.53	9	0.18	3.00	4.00
5. Comfortable communicating at EOL	3.67	0.50	9	0.17	3.00	4.00
6. Activities & resources	4.22	0.67	9	0.22	3.00	5.00
7. Will use ELNEC	4.56	0.73	9	0.24	3.00	5.00

Note: EOL = End of Life

Summary statistics were calculated for total score. Nine individuals participated in the evaluation of the program that involved answering seven questions. The average score was 27.56 ($SD = 3.00$, $SE_M = 1.00$, $Min = 22.00$, $Max = 32.00$).

A Cronbach alpha coefficient was calculated for the program evaluation scores, consisting of Questions 1 through 7. The Cronbach's alpha coefficient was evaluated using the guidelines suggested where $> .9$ excellent, $> .8$ good, $> .7$ acceptable, $> .6$ questionable, $> .5$ poor, and $\leq .5$ unacceptable. The items had a Cronbach's alpha coefficient of 0.79, indicating acceptable reliability. Table 11 presents the results of the reliability analysis.

Table 11

Reliability Table for Scores

Scale	No. of Items	α	Lower Bound	Upper Bound
Scores	7	0.79	0.62	0.96

Note. The lower and upper bounds of Cronbach's α were calculated using a 95% confidence interval.

Discussion

This section discusses the results, implications, and limitations of the project and provides recommendations for future projects. The demand for end-of-life (EOL) care is increasing and will continue to grow as the population of aging Americans increases (Population Reference Bureau, 2016; Tedder et al., 2017). This increased need for EOL care calls for healthcare professionals, including nurses, to be knowledgeable and competent EOL care providers. The expansion of the hospice nurse role has also created a need for professional training in essential communication skills and responsibilities. For example, because of their training, hospice nurses are now able to share difficult and challenging news with patients and families about disease progression or a poor medical prognosis, whereas in the past this type of information was not provided by nurses.

Hospice care depends upon the nurse's ability to provide early and ongoing assessment of patient and family care needs. The hospice nurse needs to be flexible and fluid in communicating to patients and their families, which includes the ability to interpret medical jargon, procedures, and treatment. The hospice nurse must also be able to manage conflict between family members and convey support in decision-making about care. Communication remains critical to facilitating hospice care access, making it necessary for nurses to define and describe the scope of hospice care services to patients. This QI project aimed to train hospice care nurses in effective communication with patients at the EOL and their caregivers. The author used the ELNEC Module Communication and the COMFORT communication curriculum to build an educational program that was effective in improving nurses' knowledge of primary hospice care, including EOL care.

Glover et al. (2017) compared pre-and post-questionnaires of senior nursing students' acquisition of communication and knowledge about EOL during ELNEC core training, including communication skills. Their results showed significant improvement in nursing students' knowledge and communication skills ($P < .05$) based on responses to the ELNEC Tool. Malloy's (2010) survey demonstrated that nurses who had less experience (<10 years) reported having more difficulties than experienced nurses (> 10 years), specifically when talking with family members with seriously ill patients. The narratives collected demonstrated powerful and often emotional accounts by the nurses' regarding their experiences (Malloy et al., 2010). It was revealed that communication was challenging for nurses but was vital for patient care. Therefore, the tool used by Malloy et al. (2010) was determined to be reliable and valid, though the results showed different findings between experienced (Mean 4.4) and less experienced (Mean 5.1) nurses. The project author used Malloy's (2010) tool of Self-efficacy in the present project.

This educational program was the first QI training project conducted at the CCH healthcare facility. The QI project provided knowledge about effective communication skills for nurses working with patients and their families during the challenging times of EOL and assessed nurses' confidence in their ability to communicate effectively in providing comfort care to patients at EOL. The study design involved assessing self-reports of knowledge and self-efficacy associated with communication strategies during EOL care. A pre- and post-test design was used to assess the effectiveness of an educational training program. The educational training in communication resulted in an improved sense of self-confidence in EOL communication and decision-making among patients and their families based upon a comparison of nurses' pre- and post-self-efficacy test scores and positive comments written by nurses on their program evaluation survey. Knowledge scores likewise increased post-program completion with similar

positive comments by participants saying how the program increased their knowledge of how to better communicate.

The project was pivotal in providing CCH nurses with enhanced education about communication, especially considering the timeframe of the COVID-19 global pandemic. The project had its limitation because of the COVID-19 pandemic that caused uncertainty due to lockdowns that limited the nurses' availability in visiting patients' day-to-day. This pandemic made conducting this QI project difficult since the original pre-COVID-19 plan for training for the education program was not possible due to social distancing and restricted face-to-face requirements. Therefore, the project was completed after COVID-19 vaccinations were administered to the nurses, nursing home residents, and other vulnerable hospice patients. When the nurses were brought back to work, the educational program was completed. However, the educational training was shortened from four one-hour sessions to two, two-hour sessions, which was done to accommodate nurses' schedules and decrease exposure to COVID-19.

This QI project expands the existing research on EOL communication training and documents the utility of providing face to face communication training to hospice care nurses at the CCH facility. Keeping in mind COVID-19 pandemic guideline the training followed social distancing of six feet, the wearing of masks, handwashing, and sanitizing. The CCH had a large conference room where nine participants with the trainer were accommodated and face to face training was conducted.

This training's objectives were achieved using the ELNEC and COMFORT communication educational materials for CCH hospice nurses. The results indicated that participating in the ELNEC/COMFORT training improved the CCH nurses' knowledge about EOL care, especially in content areas related to hospice care, symptom management, and

communication. In addition to the finding of significant improvement in post-test knowledge of how to effectively communicate with patients and families, comments from participants were very positive about their enhanced level of knowledge. The participants' remarks made during the debriefing session, which occurred after the role play sessions, and their written comments supported the use of role plays. Examples of comments about role play included that "it helped us learn how to share bad news, talk with dying patients, and support grieving loved ones." The narrative findings also support comments from students who requested role-playing activities to help them learn how best to share bad news, talk with dying patients, and support grieving loved ones as reported by Glover et al (2017).

A pretest/posttest was implemented to measure nurses' knowledge on EOL care. Responses to several pretest items indicated that participants had basic knowledge in certain content areas, for example, pain assessment and management and core nursing principles, such as suffering, and promoting quality of life for patients and families. This is consistent with the findings in Malloy's (2010) and Glover's et al (2017) studies in which participants found it difficult to talk to patients and their families about EOL, even though they had knowledge regarding pain management and suffering. The results of this project, like those of the Glover et al. and the Malloy studies that used the ELNEC core training course, showed an improvement in knowledge about EOL care, especially in areas related to palliative care, symptom management, communication, and grief-related loss and bereavement.

A paired-samples t-test was conducted to determine if there was a significant difference between nurses' knowledge pretest and post-test scores after implementing ELNEC and COMFORT curriculum. The pretest has a mean score of 72.62% with a posttest mean of 92.30%. The paired samples t-test ($t(8) = -6.20, p < .001$) indicated significant difference based

on an alpha value of 0.05 in nurses' pre-total and post-total knowledge scores. In this case a higher post-test score indicated higher level of knowledge than pre-test score. The paired samples t-test indicated that nurses' knowledge posttest scores were significantly higher than their pretest scores. The mean scores went from 72.62% on the pretest to 92.30 % on the posttest. Therefore, an increase in knowledge improved the communication capability of the nurses in providing EOL care.

Before training, the CCH nurses' confidence in their communication (self-efficacy) skills was low in talking to patients and families regarding EOL. After the training, however, their level of confidence increased with less difficulty expressed in talking to the patients and families. The paired samples t-test ($t(8) = 3.41, p = .009$) indicated significant differences based on an alpha value of 0.05 in the nurses' pre-total self-efficacy and post-total score scores. In this case a higher pre-test score indicated lower self-efficacy with lower posttest scores indicating higher levels of self-efficacy or confidence. Therefore, an increase in self-efficacy improved communication capability of the nurses in providing EOL care, which is consistent with Malloy's (2010) study that found nurses had high self-efficacy on post- communication training.

Findings on comfort communication and prior educational training demonstrated that communication training was needed to assist this group of nurses when talking with patients and families about EOL care. The project found wide variance in participants' comfort in communication about hospice care, EOL, and the scope of their communication abilities. This difference was similar to the Malloy (2010) and Glover et al., (2017) findings, in which the nurses' comfort levels varied in their scope of communication skillset. The narratives provided by the nurses on their reflection questions (Appendix N) addressed aspects of communication with family caregivers, which illustrates how frequently nurses support families and the

importance of communication as a key component of care. The narratives illustrate the nurses' communication concerns regarding the complexity of EOL care situations. Many of the narratives also depicted tremendous satisfaction felt by the nurses when they were able to foster effective communication after the communication training. Educational programs are needed to provide effective communication training and research is needed to evaluate the effects of communication training on patient, family, and nursing outcomes.

Clinical Practice Implications and Conclusion

The results of this QI project indicate that the implementation of the ELNEC Module 6 Communication and COMFORT communication curriculum can be a useful teaching modality for hospice nurses providing EOL care and has been determined to be successful. The project findings indicated that the ELNEC and COMFORT communication curriculum improved CCH nurses' knowledge for EOL care with statistical significance. The knowledge items had a Cronbach's alpha coefficient of 0.79, indicating acceptable reliability. The CCH nursing director was supportive in implementing this QI project in communication training using ELNEC Module 6 Communication and COMFORT communication curricula to help her hospice nurses become safe, knowledgeable, and competent at EOL care. As also demonstrated with other studies, the ELNEC and COMFORT communication has proven to be an effective means to improve nurse's knowledge (Glover et al., 2017; Malloy, 2010). The narratives provided by the participants demonstrated their communication experiences with their patients and families. The data illustrated the need for education resources to support nurses as they are involved in difficult conversations with patients at EOL and their family members. In addition, this project also demonstrated the need for skills-based learning, such as through role plays, so that nurses can practice their skills. Results of the project reveal many aspects of EOL communication that are

challenging for nurses, but mindful communication and active listening are vital for quality patient care. There are opportunities for addressing communication in hospice care and for continuing training of nurses in the clinical setting. As patients and families continue to face serious illnesses, transition to hospice care, and make difficult decisions, nurses will play a critical role and remain as the predominant professionals at the bedside.

Recommendations

Based on the findings of this QI project, the author is recommending that hospice nurses and their employment settings adopt the ELNEC and COMFORT communication curriculum to address the lack of application of EOL concepts within EOL care. The ELNEC and COMFORT communication curriculum provide a better understanding of EOL care when dealing with the patients and families and, hence, effectively prepare hospice nurses for the demanding tasks inherent in providing holistic care to patients and caregivers. Nurses must be exposed to opportunities to apply what they have learned from the ELNEC and COMFORT curriculum to understand its value. Employees should support and hospice nurses should seek additional clinical activities that will expose hospice nurses to learning opportunities related to EOL care, such as attending biannual ELNEC and COMFORT communication trainings and ELNEC and COMFORT conferences or partnering with inpatient or outpatient hospice companies for clinical learning opportunities to provide hospice nurses the opportunity to experience EOL care under supervision.

The American Nurses Association (ANA) and Hospice and Palliative Nurses Association (HPNA) are currently endorsing the ELNEC and COMFORT curriculum as the standardized palliative care nursing curriculum. This training should also be adopted for all undergraduate, graduate, and doctoral levels nursing programs (ANA & HPNA, 2017).

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APPENDIX A

PDSA Model: Model for Improvement: Plan-Do-Study-Act Cycle

Note. Used for learning how best to develop, implement, analyze, and evaluate change, (Provost & Murray, 2011)

APPENDIX B

Figure B.

Summary of the Literature Search for EOL /Nurses Communication

APPENDIX C

Outline of Training Course: ELNEC (Module 6 Communication Revised 2017)

Outline of the Course: ELNEC Communication Module 6
<p>I. DEFINITION/OVERVIEW</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> A. Effective communication B. Role of communication <ul style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Establish goals of care 2. Discuss barriers to care 3. Facilitate interaction within the interdisciplinary team <p>II. BARRIERS TO COMMUNICATION</p> <p>III. MYTHS/REALITIES OF COMMUNICATION</p> <p>IV. THE COMMUNICATION PROCESS</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> A. Patient/family expectations B. Team expectations C. Recognize individuality D. Initiate family meetings E. Palliative care planning F. Verbal and non-verbal communication G. Cultural considerations H. Listening/silence I. Presence J. Guidelines for encouraging free conversation <p>V. COMMUNICATION TECHNIQUES</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> A. Build trust B. Acknowledge emotions C. Check/verify what was said/was heard & understood D. Expect conflict E. Summarize what was understood F. Support patient/family <p>VI. INTERDISCIPLINARY TEAM/FAMILY MEMBERS</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> A. Healthcare professionals influence communication outcomes B. Family meetings to enhance communication C. Timing for conversation D. Team communication E. Resolving conflict <p>VII. SUMMARY</p>

APPENDIX D

ELNEC Module 6 Case Study

Case Study: Mr. Jones: Breaking Bad News to Family

You have received a hospice referral for Mr. Jones, age 54, who has ALS (amyotrophic lateral sclerosis). He and his family (wife and three children—ages 9, 16, 19), who are confused and anxious, listen to you as you describe what they should expect from the hospice experience. The family does not seem to understand why you are discussing end-of-life issues with them. You call Mr. Jones' family physician, who tells you that the patient assured him that he talked to his family about his prognosis. You determine that Mr. Jones has, in fact, not told his family. You talk with Mr. Jones, who admits that he has told his family he is very stable and expected to have many years of life remaining. He asks you to help him break the reality of his poor prognosis to his family.

Discussion Questions:

1. What is your role now?
2. What communication gaps do you recognize?
3. What strategies would promote continuity of care and improve team communication?
4. How might a family meeting be helpful in this case?
5. What special needs would you perceive the children having at this time? How would you meet these needs?

Please Note: All case studies are intended to be generic so that substitutions can be made, according to your own clinical roles. Feel free to adjust the case studies, so they are relevant to your participant's clinical needs.

APPENDIX E

COMFORT Communication Module 7

COMFORT: Seven Principles to Practice

The COMFORT Initiative		Early Palliative Care with Patient and Caregiver/Family
C	Communicate	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Narrative clinical practice • Verbal clarity • Non-verbal immediacy (eye contact, attentiveness, self-awareness)
O	Orientation and Opportunity	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Support health literacy • Acknowledge vulnerability • Formulate pathway of care
M	Mindfulness	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Staying in the moment • Lack of pre-judgment • Adaptation to rapid changes
F	Family	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Family as a second-order patient • Family as a conduit to the patient • Family meetings, to help clarify goals of care for the patient
O	Oversight	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Installation of coordinated care • Relieving caregiver/patient burden in complicated cases is part of oversight care
R	Reiterative and Radically Adaptive	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Time invested and quality of encounter is most important • Non-linear communication • Patient acceptability drives communication
T	Team	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Inter/multidisciplinary team members trained in various aspects of palliative care • Non-abandonment assurance • Continuity of care

Note. Source: Wittenberg-Lyles, E., Goldsmith, J., & Ragan, S.L. (2010). The COMFORT initiative: Palliative nursing and the centrality of communication. *Journal of Hospice and Palliative Nursing*, 12(5), p.285. Reprinted from *Dying with comfort: illness narratives and early palliative care*, E. Wittenberg-Lyles et al., copyright 2010b Hampton Press, Inc. Reprinted with permission of the publisher.

APPENDIX F

ELNEC Module 6 and COMFORT TMSM Communication – Lesson Plan # 1

All the materials in this training is used from ELNEC training. ELNEC Module 6 and COMFORT TMSM Communication training materials are used for each of the content areas identified in the four sessions.

Introduction to ELNEC/COMFORT

The End-of-Life Nursing Education Consortium (ELNEC) Project is a national end-of-life educational program administered by City of Hope (COH) and the American Association of Colleges of Nursing (AACN) designed to enhance palliative care in nursing. The ELNEC Project was originally funded by a grant from The Robert Wood Johnson Foundation with additional support from funding organizations: Aetna Foundation, Archstone Foundation, California HealthCare Foundation, Cambia Health Foundation, Milbank Foundation, National Cancer Institute, Oncology Nursing Foundation, Open Society Institute/Foundation, Stupski Foundation, US Cancer Pain Relief Committee and the US Department of Veterans Affairs. Further information about the ELNEC Project can be found at www.aacnnursing.org/ELNEC
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Module Overview

ELNEC module 6 emphasizes the importance of respectful and interactive communication in end-of-life care. The complexities of communicating with patients and families at this critical time are described along with suggestions for care. COMFORT Module provide communication skills training that comprehensively includes assessment of communication training needs, curriculum, and evaluation.

This module is intended to be interactive. Suggested timeframe for a one-hour presentation: 20 minutes- present slide content, 10 minutes- listening exercise (5 min of listening and 5 min to debrief) and 10 minutes -Case study reviews and role play. 20 minutes – Using ELNEC training material.

Key Messages

- Communication is critical in all healthcare situations but is of special significance at the end of life.
- Strong collaboration and communication between professionals are a prerequisite to communication with patients and families.
- Hospice nursing care requires skill in verbal and non-verbal communication, listening, and presence.

Objectives

At the completion of this modules, the participant will be able to:

1. Define communication concepts for patient centered communication throughout an end-of-life.
2. Identify and describe three factors that influence communication in the hospice care setting.
3. Recognize a variety of communication tools for practicing patient-centered care.
4. Apply new skills to case scenarios and promote self-reflection of communication.
5. Provide resources for teaching and evaluating communication.
6. Apply new skills to case scenarios and promote self-reflection of communication.
7. Identify communication characteristics that patient/families expect of healthcare professionals.

Overview of Contents: *All the materials in this training is used from ELNEC training. ELNEC Module 6 and COMFORT^{TMSM} Communication training materials are used for each of the content areas identified in the four sessions*

1. Overview of Communication
2. COMFORT^{TMSM} Curricula
3. Interdisciplinary Team
4. Key Communication Phrase
5. Review & Summary

Demographics data questionnaire

Nurses Knowledge of EOL: Modified from ELNEC

ELNEC: Modified Pre/ Post Questionnaires

Narrative (reflection) pre/post regarding communication at EOL

Nurses' Perceived Self-Efficacy

***This ends Lesson I.**

APPENDIX G

ELNEC Module 6 and COMFORT ^{TMSM} Communication – Lesson Plan # 2

CONTENTS: *All the materials in this training is used from ELNEC training. ELNEC Module 6 and COMFORT ^{TMSM} Communication training materials are used for each of the content areas identified in the four sessions*

1. Overview of Communication

- 1.1. Communication
- 1.2. Three Journey Affected by Communication
 - 1.2.1. Isolated Journey-- the absence of hospice care (example- closed awareness of how ill the patient is.
 - 1.2.2. Rescued Journey- Rescued Journey – rescued from isolated journey through sudden referral to hospice care (example- Patient/family suddenly aware of the seriousness of the illness).
 - 1.2.3. Comforted Journey- Moving to hospice care EOL (example- awareness of what disease and prognosis are- communication is explicit).
- 1.3. Patient and Family Expectation
- 1.4. Communication Across the Illness Trajectory
- 1.5. Communication with Patient and Family
- 1.6. Key Statements to Use
- 1.7. Ethical Emphasis
- 1.8. Barriers to Communication
- 1.9. Myths of Communication
- 1.10. Caregivers Assessment Questions
- 1.11. Verbal and Non-verbal Communication
- 1.12. Cultural Consideration
- 1.13. Guideline for Encouraging Conversation
- 1.14. Communication: Stages of Nurse-patient Relationship
- 1.15. Attentive Listening- Listening Steps
- 1.16. Mindful Presence
- 1.17. Listening Exercise

Time: 5 minutes

- Two people
 - One listens without interrupting
 - One speaks about a loss (for 5 minutes)

Review/Summary

***This ends Lesson 2.**

APPENDIX H

ELNEC Module 6 and COMFORT^{TMSM} Communication – Lesson Plan # 3

CONTENTS: *All the materials in this training is used from ELNEC training. ELNEC Module 6 and COMFORT^{TMSM} Communication training materials are used for each of the content areas identified in the four sessions*

3. Communication Technique: Giving the “words”

- 3.1. Basic technique
- 3.2. Articulating Empathy: Nurse
- 3.3. Communication Strategies: Facilitating End-of-Life (EOL) Decision
- 3.4. Establishing Goals of Care
- 3.5. COMFORT Communication Initiative (skills)
- 3.6. Addressing Goals of Care: REMAP

Time: 10 mins.

Exercise to Elicit End-of-Life Goals (Brief role play)

Questions to Ask Patients & Families to Help Them Identify What is Important About This time in Their Lives, Their End-of-Life Goals, Wishes and Plans (

- 3.7. I'M Sorry vs I Wish
- 3.8. Communicating Unexpected Death
- 3.9. Communication Pearls

Time: 5mins.

Case Study

Review/Summary

***This ends Lesson 3**

APPENDIX I

ELNEC Module 6 and COMFORT^{TMSM} Communication – Lesson Plan # 4

CONTENTS: *All the materials in this training is used from ELNEC training. ELNEC Module 6 and COMFORT^{TMSM} Communication training materials are used for each of the content areas identified in the four sessions*

4. The Interdisciplinary Team and Family Members

- 4.1. Healthcare Professionals Influence on Communication Outcomes
- 4.2. Family Meetings: Family Members and Caregivers
- 4.3. Why They Are Important
- 4.4. Six-Step Protocol for Breaking Bad News
- 4.5. Issues of Communication and Shared Decision-Making
- 4.6. Recommendations for Conducting a Family Meeting
- 4.7. Articulate the Benefits: How do I articulate the way hospice care can help?
- 4.8. Timing for Conversation is Critical
- 4.9. Team Communication
- 4.10. Pay Attention to the Conflict
- 4.11. Resolving Conflicts

Time: 5mins.

Exercise on Conflict: Play role

Review/Summary

Nurses Knowledge of EOL: Modified from ELNEC

ELNEC: Modified Pre/ Post Questionnaires

Narrative (reflection) pre/post regarding communication at EOL

Nurses' Perceived Self-Efficacy

Pre/Post

Nurses Evaluation of Communication Training

***This ends Lesson 4**

***Next Evaluation will be after 2 months for Quality Improvement (QI).**

APPENDIX J**Tool 1: Nurses' Demographics (6 items)**

Demographic Information

1. Number of years in the nursing profession ____
2. Number of years in hospice care ____
3. Which range below represents your age? 19-25 () 26-35 () 36 + ()
4. How do you identify your gender? Female () Male ()
5. Race/Ethnicity: White /Nonhispanic () Native American () White/Hispanic () African American () Asian/Pacific Islanders () Other ()
6. Education: College () Undergraduate () Graduate () Other ()

APPENDIX K

Tool 2: Nurses Knowledge of EOL: Modified from ELNEC

ELNEC: Modified Pre/Post Questionnaires (13 Items)

(ELNEC Scoring: 90-100% -No difficulty in communication; 70-80%- Somewhat difficult; 50-60%- difficult; 10-40% -very difficult)

Q.1. Which of the following is the best strategy to resolve conflict?

- a. Identify your own emotions and try to describe them to the patient.
- b. Identify the areas of conflict, recognizing that they never are fully resolved.
- c. Provide patient and family with more information, and eventually everyone will agree
- d. Discuss areas of conflict with each family member separately instead of in a family meeting

Q.2. True or False: When someone is in emotional shock after receiving bad news, the hospice nurse should outline practical "next steps" that should be taken immediately and wait to discuss what can be addressed later. Identify your own emotions and try to describe them to the patient.

- a. True
- b. False

Q.3. You are working with a new team member on the effective communication technique to use when talking to patients and families which of the following statements from the team member indicates that they have a good understanding of basic technique?

- a. I should not use the word death and dying in my conversation
- b. I should assume that the patient and family have understood what I have told them.
- c. I need to be sure to fill in any gaps in the conversation with more information
- d. I should acknowledge the emotions that the patient and family are expressing.

Q.4. Which of the following is a component of mindful presence?

- a. Denial of oneself
- b. Marking vulnerability
- c. Being in moment
- d. Avoiding silence

Q.5. Which of the following actions by hospice nurse opens the communication process when speaking with a patient?

- a. Find out if the patient feels like talking
- b. Remain standing during a conversation
- c. Interrupt and correct the patient if they have misinformation
- d. Discuss medical issues first to relax the patient

Q.6. What is the most critical purpose of the family meeting?

- a. To determine hospice eligibility
- b. To build trust
- c. To determine which information to avoid sharing
- d. To communicate with the team's preset goals of care

Q.7. You are caring for a patient who is at the end stage of disease ovarian cancer and has four months to live. She does not know her diagnosis. Which action should you take in preparation for the patient to be told her diagnosis and prognosis?

- a. Resolve to interrupt the patient as needed and correct misinformation
- b. Decide to give limited information to support a perception of hope.
- c. Find out how much the patient and family want to know
- d. Research thoroughly to give as much information as possible at once

Q 8. Which of the following communication strategies would be the Best for facilitating EOL decisions?

- a. Be willing to initiate and engage in discussions about EOL care
- b. Avoid giving any type of hope to the patient and family
- c. Emphasize the burdens of treatment options
- d. Allow each team member to express their different opinions to the patient

Q.9. Which of the following do many patients at EOL expect from hospice nurses?

- a. A hospice nurse will be honest and truthful in communication
- b. A hospice nurse will not necessarily discuss the patient's care.
- c. A hospice nurse will decide what patient issues need to be addressed first
- d. A hospice nurse will give advice

Q. 10. You are facilitating a staff discussion about myths and realities of communication in hospice care, which is a correct statement about communication?

- a. We can never give someone too much information
- b. We communicate when we choose to communicate
- c. The majority of messages we send are non-verbal
- d. Communication is primarily words and meanings

Q. 11. An 85-year-old patient with the end-stage disease is dying. You find the daughter crying by the patient's bedside. Which intervention is most appropriate in communicating with this family member?

- a. Ask the daughter if she would like to reconsider treatment
- b. Talk to the physician about moving the patient to a hospice care unit
- c. Remain present with the daughter, using silence to impart comfort.
- d. Assure that daughter that she does not need to stay with her mother

Q.12. True or False: It is better to use "I'm sorry "rather than "I wish."

- a. True. b. False

Q. 13. True or False: Understanding a patient's real belief is an essential aspect of Q communication.

- a. True. b. False

Last Question: Narrative (reflection) pre/post regarding communication at EOL

Q. 14. Your reflections regarding communication and EOL?

Please write a sentence or two describing each of these areas:

- Your comfort level and ease in communicating with patients (their loved ones) and caregivers (patients' loved ones) about pain and symptom control during the EOL stage of a terminal illness.

- Your comfort level and ease in communicating with patients (their loved ones) and caregivers (patients' loved ones) about their spiritual needs and or concerns about suffering and or death during the EOL stage of a terminal illness.
- Your comfort level and ease in communicating with patients and caregivers about their concerns with burden of care or the strain that their loved ones may be experiencing during the EOL stage of their illness.

APPENDIX L

Tool 3: Self- Efficacy

-Pre/Post Communication Survey 5- Point Likert Scale

Scale from 0 = (not difficult) to 5 = (very difficult).

		Not difficult	Somewhat difficult	Neutral	Difficult	Very difficult
	Difficulty Level of Conversation	1	2	3	4	5
1	Talking with patients once they have received bad news					
2	Talking with family members of seriously ill patients					
3	Talking with patients/families about spiritual/religious concerns					
4	Discussing decisions such as advanced directives, DNR orders, feeding tubes, etc.					
5	Remaining silent and listening to painful feelings from patients/families					
6	Talking with patients or families from different cultures					
7	Talking with patients about pain and other symptoms					
8	Talking with patients or families about suffering					
9	Talking with nurse colleagues about hospice care issues					
10	Talking with families about pain and symptoms management					

APPENDIX M

Tool 4: Evaluation of Communication Training

(1-strongly disagree; 2-3 Disagree; 4-Agree; 5= strongly agree) 5 Point Likert Scale Survey

		Strongly Disagree	Disagree	Neutral	Agree	Strongly Agree
	Question	1	2	3	4	5
1	Do you think the ELNEC Module 6 and COMFORT curriculum improved your knowledge concerning the principles of hospice care?					
2	Do you think the ELNEC Module 6 and COMFORT curriculum improved your knowledge concerning communication regarding symptom management (e.g., medications) in EOL concepts?					
3	Do you think the ELNEC Module 6 and COMFORT curriculum improved your knowledge concerning EOL communication with your patients and families?					
4	Do you think the ELNEC Module 6 and COMFORT curriculum improved your knowledge concerning communication regarding cultural issues in end of life concepts?					
5	After working through the ELNEC Module 6 and COMFORT, how prepared you feel to provided communication skills at the end of life care?					
6	The activities/ interactions and resources enhanced the effectiveness of this activity					
7	Do you plan on using what you learned from the ELNEC Module 6 and COMFORT curriculum (open-ended) in your workplace (Hospice/EOL)?					

APPENDIX N

Permission from City of Hope and ELNEC

smoledina55@gmail.com

From: Rose Virani <RVirani@coh.org>
Sent: Monday, August 3, 2020 12:49 PM
To: Shabnam_Moledina@msn.com; smoledina55@gmail.com
Cc: Rose Virani
Subject: Permission for ELNEC materials
Attachments: ELNEC Copyright Permission 2020.pdf

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I have attached the ELNEC copyright permission statement from ELNEC.

Best wishes in your studies and don't hesitate to contact me should you have any questions,

Thank you,

Rose

Rose Virani RNC, MHA, FPCN
 Sr. Research Specialist/ELNEC Project Director
 City of Hope
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 Duarte, CA 91010
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APPENDIX O

Permission from City of Hope/ ELNEC to use Communication Survey

Shabnam_Moledina@msn.com

From: shabnam_moledina@msn.com
To: smoledina55@gmail.com
Subject: FW: Communication Survey permission
Attachments: 2010_Communication Survey_JHPN.doc

From: Rose Virani <RVirani@coh.org>
Sent: Monday, August 3, 2020 11:55 AM
To: Shabnam_Moledina@msn.com; smoledina55@gmail.com
Subject: Communication Survey permission

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Should you have any questions, please don't hesitate to contact me.

Thank you,
Rose

Rose Virani RNC, MHA, FPCN
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APPENDIX P

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ELNEC Project Copyright Permission
Updated: February 2020

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For further information or questions, contact ELNEC Project Office at elnecc@coh.org.

APPENDIX Q

Letter of Support from Community Care Hospice

Community Care Hospice
of Glendora

Date: July 23, 2020

From: Vivian Gracie-Allen,
Executive Director
Community Care Hospice
222 West Foothill Boulevard
Glendora, CA 91741

To: Institute of Review Board (IRB)
California State University, Long Beach
1250 N Bellflower Blvd,
Long Beach, CA 90840

Re: Doctor of Nursing Practice Project

I am writing this letter at the request of student Shabnam Mehdinia to confirm that we are working with her as she commences her Quality Improvement Project, "Increasing Communication Skills of Community Care Hospice Nurses Using CILNEC communication Materials/Modules."

I am aware that she will be conducting educational training Quality Improvement Project on communication skills for our hospice nurses. Shabnam has our approval to conduct the above educational training as long as she has IRB approval to do so.

I also confirm that employees/nurses here at Community Care Hospice will participate in the Quality Improvement Project training on Communication skills. There will be no involvement of patients in this training program.

Should any organizational problems occur, it is up to Shabnam to report these events to the IRB at your school and the Community Care Hospice Executive Director, promptly.

Shabnam Mehdinia's quality improvement project will be a valuable contribution to the improvement of our hospice nurses' communication skills. We are delighted to support Shabnam in this endeavor.

If you have any questions regarding the above-mentioned training project, please feel free to call me at (626) 335-9759.

Sincerely,

Vivian Gracie-Allen, R.N.

Executive Director

222 West Foothill Boulevard • Glendora, California 91741
Tel: (626) 335-9759 • Fax: (626) 335-5688 • Email: (626) 335-5689

APPENDIX R**Approval Letter from Institutional Review Board, California State University, Long Beach****CALIFORNIA STATE UNIVERSITY, LONG
BEACH****OFFICE OF RESEARCH & SPONSORED PROGRAMS**

DATE: November 12, 2020

TO: Shabnam Moledina, DNP Student

FROM: CSULB IRB

PROJECT TITLE: [1660502-3] Increasing Communication Skills of Community Care
Hospice Nurses Using ELNEC Communication
Materials/Modules

REFERENCE #: 21-064

SUBMISSION TYPE: New Project

REVIEW TYPE: Exempt Review

ACTION: APPROVED APPROVAL DATE:

November 12, 2020

This is to advise you that the Institutional Review Board for the Protection of Human Subjects (IRB) of California State University, Long Beach, has reviewed your protocol application.

Your application is approved by Exempt Review according to the U.S. Department of Health & Human Services regulation at 45 CFR 46.104(d)(3).

Note: The researcher must follow all COVID-19 Policies and Procedures implemented at Community Care Hospice.

Approval is effective beginning November 12, 2020 and conditional upon your willingness to carry out your continuing responsibilities under University policy:

1. You must clearly indicate in the header or footer of each page of your approved Informed Consent Form and recruitment material as follows: "**Approved November 12, 2020 by the CSULB IRB.**"
2. If you need to make changes/revisions to this approved project, you must submit a Request for Amendment to an Approved Protocol form in addition to any documents affected by the requested change. Submit these documents as a subsequent package to your approved project in IRBNet. You are not allowed to implement any changes to your research activities prior to obtaining final approval of your Amendment from the CSULB IRB.
3. You are required to inform the Director of Research Integrity and Compliance, Office of Research & Sponsored Programs, via email at ORSPCompliance within twenty-four hours of any adverse event in the conduct of research involving human subjects. The report shall include the nature of the adverse event, the names of the persons affected, the extent of the injury or breach of confidentiality or data security, if any, and any other information material to the situation.
4. Maintain your research records as detailed in the protocol.

Should you have any questions about the conduct of your research under this protocol, particularly about providing informed consent and unexpected contingencies, please do not hesitate to call the Office of Research & Sponsored Programs at (562) 985-8147. We wish you the best of success in your research.

This letter has been electronically signed in accordance with all applicable regulations, and a copy is retained within California State University, Long Beach Institutional Review Board's records.

1250 Bellflower Blvd., Long Beach, CA
90840
Ph. (562) 985-8147 Fax. (562) 985-8665

APPENDIX S

Notice of Informed Consent

Project Title: [1660502-2] Increasing Communication Skills of Community Care Hospice Nurses Using ELNEC Communication Materials /Modules.

Investigator(s): PI, Shabnam Moledina, DNP Student. Co-Investigator(s) None

Project Contact: 562-556-8821

**California State University, Long Beach (CSULB), Office of Research and Sponsored Programs,
CSULB: 1250 Bellflower Blvd., Long Beach, CA 90840**

You are being asked to participate in a research study.

The purpose of this study is to “Increase Communication Skills of Community Care Hospice Nurses Using ELNEC Communication Materials/Modules.” If you decide to participate you will be asked: to complete four questionnaires. 1. Nurses’ Demographics; 2. Nurse’s knowledge of End-of-Life care at baseline and post questionnaires; 3. Nurses self-efficacy with conducting End-of-Life conversation at baseline and post survey; and 4. Nurse evaluation at the end of the training which are all for research purposes. The total time of your participation is expected to one hour every two weeks for total of four sessions. The risks to participating in this study include:

1. Concern that your responses to pre- and post-testing and questionnaires will be shared with the director and affect your employment status.
2. The possibility of computer hacking and or a break in where the questionnaires are kept.
3. Fear of coercion from your employer related to complete the project questionnaires.

The investigator will make every attempt to reduce these risks by:

1. Only aggregate scoring data will be shared with the director.
2. The questionnaires/tests will have specific code to link the participants’ pre- and post-data that you will determine and data collected from the CCH nurses will be kept confidential and secured in a password-protected computer that is accessed by the project author only

The paper and pencil tests will be stored in Project author’s office in a locked cabinet.

3. You will be given a handout that notes individuals are free to opt out by turning blank questionnaires.
- 4.

You may directly benefit from participating in this study as participants will gain knowledge to improve their communication skills at the EOL. However, the results of this study may benefit the hospice patients you serve as you will be educated about effective communication strategies that benefit patients at the EOL and their loved ones.

Any information collected from you in this study will be stored in a secure location and will not be shared with anyone who does not have appreciate provisions to access the information.

You may contact the Office of Research and Sponsored Programs at ORSPCompliance@csulb.edu, or calling (562) 985-8147, if you have questions about your rights as a research participant.

Signing this document means that all information about the study has been explained to you orally, the investigator has answered any questions you have about the study and that you voluntarily agree to participate.

Name of Subject (Printed)

Subject Signature

Date

APPENDIX T

Responses to Question 14 by Nurses (N): Reflection Regarding Communication at EOL

Your comfort level and ease in communicating with patients and caregivers about pain and symptom control during the EOL stage of a terminal illness.

Pre-Questionnaire Responses	Post-Questionnaire Responses
N1 - No comments	N1- After attending the training on Comfort/ELNEC communication training, I feel comfortable talking to patient and family.
N2 - Every family is different from coping with pain, which need to assess during pain and discuss with the family.	N2 - My comfort of talking to patient and family regarding pain is better after this communication training. But each family deals different to pain /symptoms.
N3 - No comment	N3 - I am comfortable talking to patient and family regarding pain.
N4 - Not to sedate but rather comfort patient so that they may have a better quality.	N4 - Oral sedation should not be given-feel comfortable talking to patient/caregiver about pain/symptoms.
N5 - Every patient & family/caregiver are different.	N5 - Feeling comfortable talking about pain/symptoms though each patient & family /caregivers are differently behaving.
N6 - I would sit down, face to face, with the patient/caregivers, maintain eye contact and holding their hands. Listen to the patient express their symptoms and voice their fear about impending death.	N6 - By listening to patient and caregiver regarding pain/symptoms. I feel comfortable in assisting them.
N7 - No comment	N7 - No comment.
N8- No comment	N8 - I will be able to communicate with patients and caregivers better after this training.
N9 - No comment	N9 - No comment

Your comfort level and ease in communicating with patient and caregivers about their spiritual needs and or concerns about suffering and or death during EOL stage.

Pre-Questionnaire Responses	Post- Questionnaire Responses
N1 - No comment	N1 - Always felt good talking about spirituality.
N2 - No comment	N2 - I am not sure about spirituality. Normally they talk to their chaplain.
N3 - No comment	N3 - No issues talking about spiritual needs.
N4 - Anxiety is just as bad as pain.	N4 - Talking about death is anxiety - spirituality is personal but the priest/chaplain should be involved.
N5 - Tend to differ to spiritual care (resources).	N5 - Do not talk much about spiritual needs, because chaplain visits them very often.
N6 - I would ask the patient if he/she wanted the hospice to call a religious person to visit or if they want the family to do so.	N6 - I do not feel comfortable but would encourage to call chaplain.
N7 - No comment	N7 - No comment
N8 - No comment	N8 - It has always been easy for me to talk about spiritual needs
N9 - No comment	N9 - No comment

Your comfort level and ease in communicating with patients and caregivers about their concerns with burden of care or the strain that their loved ones may be experiencing during the EOL stage of their illness.

Pre-Questionnaire Responses	Post-Questionnaire Responses
N1 - No comment	N1- It was difficult initially to talk to patients and caregivers/families regarding their concern about their care and burden, but after the first training I am able to understand the needs of the patient and their caregivers especially with second training and case study. I feel I will be able to better communicate on this issue.
N2 - No comment	N2 - I have seen some families/caregivers feel that the burden of care but do have lots of concerns. I think I feel better that I will be able to communicate better after the training.
N3- No comment	N3 - I have seen lots of different reaction from caregiver/patients but I am able to assist them.
N4 - Providing the best gift and that is being at home with family.	N4 - Feel comfortable talking to patient/caregivers.
N5 - Will talk to them about options.	N5 - Give options of treatment and encourage to seek support systems.

N6 - We can increase the frequency of pain relief medication and provide support for the well-being of the family.	N6 -I am feeling good after the training that I will be able to assist and support caregivers/family and the patients for their needs, so they do not feel the burden of care.
N7 - No comment	N7 - No comment
N8 - No comment	N8 - I feel I will be better in communication after this training.
N9- No comment	N9 - No comment

**Grouping of Narrative Questions: Reflection regarding communication at EOL
Responses from Participants**

Pre-Questions Responses	Post- Questions Responses
Pain and Symptoms	
N1, N3, N7, N8, N9 - No responses N2, N5 - Every family is different in coping with pain, which need to assess during pain and discussion with the family. N4, N6 - Comfort patient by listening, eye contact, holding hand and patient to express their pain and symptoms.	N7, N9 - No responses N1, N2, N8 - After communication training I feel comfortable talking to patients and families/caregivers. N3, N5, N6 - Feel comfortable talking to patients and families/caregivers. N4 - Avoid oral sedation, feel comfortable talking to patient and family.
Spiritual Needs and or Concerns About Suffering and or Death	
N1, N2, N3, N7, N8, N9 - No response N4 - Anxiety talking about spiritual and death. N5 - Tend to differ from spiritual care (resources) N6 - Offer priest or chaplain to visit	N1, N3, N8 - Comfortable talking about spirituality. N2, N5, N6 - Feel uncomfortable talking about spirituality, usually call chaplain. N4 - Anxiety talking about death and spirituality is personal -priest or chaplain should be involved. N7, N9 - No response
Burden of Care or Strain Loved Ones May Experience	
N1, N2, N3, N7, N8, N9 - No Response N4 - Providing gift of staying home. N5 - Talk about options N6 - Increase pain relief medication and provide support.	N1, N2, N6, N8 - After the training, feel comfortable to talk about burden of care. N3, N4 - Able to assist comfortably. N5 - Option of care and resources N7, N9 - No response